

ORGANIZATIONAL SOCIAL CONTEXT AND TEACHER ACADEMIC OPTIMISM

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Sarangani District of Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2025-2026. Research instruments on organizational social context and teacher academic optimism were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: The study found to exhibit a very high level of organizational social context. This means that the provisions relating to organizational social context is always observed. The study revealed a very high level of teacher academic optimism. This indicates that the provisions relating to student interaction are embodied in the item is always observed. The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism. This implies that the higher the organizational social context, the higher is the teacher academic optimism. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism was rejected.

Keywords: organizational social context, teacher academic optimism, school administration and supervision, quantitative research.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teacher academic optimism refers to educators' positive belief in their ability to influence student learning and success, regardless of external challenges. However, various issues can hinder teachers from maintaining a high level of academic optimism, teacher stress tops the list. In Australia, 90% of teachers report moderate to extremely severe levels of stress. One major problem is the overwhelming workload and pressure that teachers face. These teachers admitted that they are burdened with excessive administrative tasks, grading, and lesson planning, leaving them with limited time to focus on teaching and fostering positive academic beliefs (Carroll, Forrest, Sanders-O'Connor, Flynn, Bower, Fynes-Clinton & Ziaei, 2022).

In most situation, teacher stress can lead to burnout, which in turn diminishes their optimism about their ability to make a difference in their students' lives. When teachers feel overworked and underappreciated, their sense of efficacy and hope for student success can quickly fade. This is the common case in China. A comprehensive review on teacher burnout in China found that Chinese educators report the second-highest scores on emotional exhaustion among teachers from 35 nations, signaling very intense psychological strain (Tsang, Teng, Lian & Wang, 2021).

Another significant issue that undermine teacher academic optimism teacher academic optimism is the challenging student behaviors and lack of engagement. In classrooms where students exhibit lack of motivation, or show little interest in learning, teachers may struggle to maintain their belief in their ability to foster success. In the Philippines, this problem is so common that 8 in every 10 teachers reported that lack of interest of students is one leading cause to poor academic

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performance. Teachers working with such students may start to feel disillusioned and question whether their efforts are truly making a difference, leading to a decline in their overall academic optimism (Montano, 2021).

Another obstacle to teacher academic optimism in the country is the standardized testing culture that dominates many educational systems. Teachers often feel constrained by the pressure to prepare students for high-stakes assessments, which can limit their ability to focus on holistic, meaningful learning. The constant focus on test scores can diminish teachers' belief in their ability to nurture a well-rounded education, causing them to prioritize test preparation over fostering critical thinking, creativity, and deep learning. This narrow view of student success can lead teachers to feel less empowered, as their ability to influence students' futures seems restricted to test outcomes alone (Trinidad, 2020).

Meanwhile, some teachers in the division of Davao Occidental has felt the fading academic optimism that stems from societal factors and public perception of teaching which also impact teacher academic optimism. Teachers often face negative stereotypes about their profession, such as being underpaid, undervalued, or blamed for broader societal issues like educational inequality. When teachers feel that their work is not respected or recognized, it becomes harder for them to remain hopeful and optimistic about their role in student success. External pressures, including public criticism can contribute to a pessimistic view of teaching as a profession, which directly affects the optimism teachers have toward their ability to make a meaningful impact on students' academic journeys.

There is a need to help teachers revive their belief in academic optimism and it takes organizational social context to be felt in schools. However, the relationship of these two variables has not been explored in the local context that it prompted the researcher to conduct this study and eventually address evidence gap which can add to the knowledge this research aims to explore.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study is aimed to find out the relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

What is the level of organizational social context in terms of:

1.1 Culture;

1.2 Climate, and

1.3 Engagement?

2. What is the level of teacher academic optimism in terms of:

2.1 Teacher Efficacy;

2.2 Teacher Trust in Students;

2.3 Teacher Trust in Students' Learning Orientation;

2.4 Teacher Trust in Parents, and

2.5 Teacher Academic Emphasis?

3. Is there a significant relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism?

Hypothesis

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational technique. Non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing a correlational technique is a type of research approach used to examine the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. It falls under quantitative research because it

involves collecting and analyzing numerical data. The term non-experimental indicates that the researcher does not control or manipulate any variables, unlike in experimental research, where treatments or interventions are applied.

Non-experimental correlational research is a research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables, without establishing cause and effect in which in this study, it will look into the relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This will be used to determine the level of organizational social context and teacher academic optimism

Pearson r. This will be used to determine the significance of the relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Organizational Social Context

Shown in Table 1 is the level of organizational social context with an overall mean of 39 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, climate has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.45 or very high, culture has a mean rating of 4.37 or very high, and empowerment has a mean rating of 4.36 or very high.

Table 1. Organizational Social Context

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Culture	4.37	Very High
Climate	4.45	Very High
Engagement	4.36	Very High
Overall	4.39	Very High

The result of the study is in consonance with the findings of Trinidad (2024) who reported that school organizational culture shape how a school functions on a daily basis. It influences how administrators, teachers, students, and families interact and work toward common goals. A strong organizational culture is built on a clear mission and vision, often guided by leadership such as the principal and supported by the district, for example a public school system like New York City Department of Education. When everyone understands and commits to shared expectations, the school environment becomes more focused, collaborative, and purpose-driven.

Such finding is corollary to the study of Orón Semper, Lizasoain, Abaurrea, González-García & Ayuga-Téllez (2021) who noted that positive school culture promotes respect, inclusivity, and continuous improvement. Teachers feel valued and supported in their professional growth, students feel safe and motivated to learn, and families feel welcomed as partners in education. Schools that emphasize collaboration, such as professional learning communities and team-based planning, tend to build trust among staff. Research and organizations like National Education Association often highlight the importance of supportive leadership and open communication in strengthening school culture and improving student outcomes.

The result of the study corresponds with the statement of Leithwood, Jantzi & Steinbach (2021) who declared that a weak or negative organizational culture can lead to low morale, poor communication, and inconsistent expectations. When there is a lack of trust or unclear leadership, staff members may work in isolation, and students may feel disconnected from the school community. Building a healthy culture requires intentional effort, including setting clear goals, recognizing achievements, addressing conflicts constructively, and modeling shared values. Ultimately, school organizational culture plays a critical role in shaping both the academic success and the overall well-being of everyone within the school community.

Level of Teacher Academic Optimism

Shown in Table 2 is the level of teacher academic optimism with an overall mean of 4.41 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, teacher academic emphasis the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.48 or very high, teacher efficacy, 4.43 or very high, teacher trust in students, 4.28 or very high, teacher's trust in students' learning orientation, 4.45 or very high, teacher trust in parent, 4.41 or very high.

The result of the study corresponds with the statement of Ateş & Ünal (2021) who suggested that teacher academic optimism is important because it directly influences student achievement, instructional quality, and the overall effectiveness of a school. When teachers believe they can help students succeed, trust their school community, and maintain high academic expectations, they create a powerful learning environment that promotes student growth.

The result of the study is consistent with the statement of Song (2022) who confirmed that one major importance of teacher academic optimism is its strong connection to student performance. Research shows that when teachers maintain high expectations and believe in their students' abilities, students are more likely to meet those expectations. Optimistic teachers persist through challenges, use effective instructional strategies, and provide consistent encouragement. This belief system fosters resilience in both teachers and students, particularly in schools facing socioeconomic challenges. Academic optimism helps counteract external factors by focusing on what educators can control, quality teaching and supportive relationships.

The result of the study supports the statement of Galindo & Sanders (2022) who acknowledged that additionally, teacher academic optimism strengthens school culture and climate. When educators collectively share confidence in their ability to make a difference, trust one another, and prioritize academic success, collaboration increases and morale improves. This collective mindset promotes professional commitment, reduces burnout, and supports continuous improvement. Ultimately, teacher academic optimism is important because it builds a foundation of belief, trust, and high expectations that drives sustained academic success for students and organizational effectiveness for schools.

Table II. Teacher Academic Optimism

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Teacher Efficacy	4.43	Very High
Teacher Trust in Students	4.28	Very High
Teacher Trust in Students' Learning Orientation	4.45	Very High
Teacher Trust in Parents	4.41	Very High
Teacher Academic Emphasis	4.48	Very High
Overall	4.41	Very High

Significance on the Relationship between Organizational Social Context and Teacher Academic Optimism

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.104 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism is rejected.

The result of the study confirms the statement of Üzümlü & Ünal (2023) who noted that the relationship between Organizational Social Context (OSC) and Teacher Academic Optimism (TAO) is deeply interconnected, as the environment and culture of a school influence teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors toward student achievement. Organizational Social Context encompasses a school's culture, climate, and engagement levels, reflecting how staff interact, communicate, and perceive the work environment. Teacher Academic Optimism, on the other hand, represents educators' belief in their efficacy, trust in students and parents, and commitment to academic excellence. A positive OSC creates conditions that reinforce and support the development of academic optimism among teachers.

The result of the study is in line with the statement of Çakır (2024) who declared that a school with a supportive climate, characterized by collaboration, shared leadership, and trust, enhances teachers’ sense of efficacy, a key component of academic optimism. When teachers experience a culture that values learning, professional growth, and high expectations, they are more likely to believe in their ability to positively influence student outcomes. Similarly, a school climate that encourages engagement and collaboration strengthens trust in students and parents, because teachers feel confident that their efforts are supported and reciprocated. Research shows that teachers in schools with high levels of organizational support are more optimistic, persistent, and willing to invest in challenging students.

The result of the study corroborates the statement of Thien & Chan (2022) who expressed that conversely, a negative organizational social context, marked by poor communication, lack of support, and low morale, can undermine teacher academic optimism. Teachers may feel isolated, powerless, or skeptical of student and parent involvement, which reduces their motivation and commitment to maintaining high academic expectations. In essence, the OSC sets the stage for academic optimism: a positive context nurtures optimism by providing resources, trust, and a culture of excellence, while a weak or toxic context diminishes it. Therefore, fostering a healthy organizational social context is crucial for sustaining teacher academic optimism and, by extension, enhancing student achievement and school effectiveness.

Table III. Significance on the Relationship between Organizational Social Context and Teacher Academic Optimism

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Organizational Social Context and Teacher Academic Optimism	0.104	0.000	Reject

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study found to exhibit a very high level of organizational social context. This means that the provisions relating to organizational social context is always observed.

The study revealed a very high level of teacher academic optimism. This indicates that the provisions relating to student interaction are embodied in the item is always observed.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism. This implies that the higher the organizational social context, the higher is the teacher academic optimism. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism was rejected.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study revealed that there is a very high level of organizational social context. The researcher recommends that the teachers may improve in the area of engagement as one indicator of organizational social context since this is the lowest among all the indicators. The researcher recommends that Teachers may seek feedback from supervisors on areas for skill development and ways to expand your responsibilities.; actively participate in available professional development programs and apply learnings in the classroom; Share knowledge gained from workshops or training sessions with colleagues to enhance collaborative learning; seek ways to make your daily tasks more meaningful by connecting them to student outcomes and personal goals; build strong relationships with colleagues and leadership to foster a sense of belonging; and reflect on professional and personal goals and identify how your current role aligns with them.

Principals may provide clear career pathways and growth opportunities for teachers, such as leadership roles, committees, or special projects; offer targeted, relevant professional development opportunities that match teacher needs and interests; create opportunities for teachers to contribute to decision-making and school initiatives; foster a collaborative, transparent culture where teachers feel their voice matters; and conduct periodic surveys or check-ins to understand teacher needs and concerns.

The study revealed a very high level of teacher academic optimism. The researcher recommends that teacher may improve in the area of the aspect of teacher trust the students as one indicators of teacher academic optimism since this is the lowest among all the indicators. Teachers may encourage open dialogue by asking students about their opinions, interests, and experiences; show genuine interest in students' lives beyond academics to build authenticity in the relationship; set clear expectations and consistently reinforce them, allowing students to demonstrate responsibility; provide opportunities for students to make decisions and take ownership of learning tasks; engage in regular, meaningful conversations to understand students' goals, challenges, and motivations; create a safe environment where students feel respected and encouraged to express themselves, making it easier for mutual vulnerability.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between organizational social context and teacher academic optimism. The researcher recommends that teachers may foster collaborative relationships by working actively with colleagues to share strategies, resources, and successes. collaboration strengthens engagement and reinforces collective efficacy; demonstrate high academic expectations by maintaining consistent focus on student learning and growth; engage in continuous professional development by participating in training and workshops to enhance skills, which supports both personal efficacy and optimism in student outcomes; build trust with students and parents by developing meaningful connections with students and maintain open communication with families to strengthen relationships and commitment; and model positive mindset by exhibiting resilience, problem-solving, and optimism in facing challenges, signaling confidence to students and colleagues.

Principals may create a supportive school climate by encouraging open communication, shared decision-making, and recognition of staff contributions to enhance teacher engagement and trust; provide clear vision and goals by establishing and communicate a shared mission that emphasizes academic excellence, collaboration, and student success; encourage teacher leadership by offering opportunities for teachers to lead initiatives, mentor colleagues, or participate in committees, fostering ownership and optimism; recognize and reward effort and achievement by regularly acknowledge teacher accomplishments, innovative practices, and student success to reinforce efficacy and morale.

District supervisors may support professional development programs by ensuring teachers have access to training that strengthens instructional skills, leadership, and academic optimism; promote consistent organizational policies by establishing clear expectations and policies that foster trust, collaboration, and engagement across schools; encourage leadership coaching by offering coaching and mentorship programs for school leaders to enhance their ability to create positive organizational social contexts, and monitor and assess school climate by using surveys and data to track teacher engagement, professional optimism, and organizational culture, then provide feedback and support for improvement.

The researcher also recommends to future researchers to conduct similar study and explore some indicators that are not included in this study in another setting in order to uncover new knowledge relevant to the topics presented in this study.

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